

5	19	V_k	m^3	$0,0792 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1,42 \cdot 10^{-10}$	-
6	19	V_n	m^3	$0,00462 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$8,90 \cdot 10^{-11}$	-
7	19	V	m^3	$7,4830 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$3,22 \cdot 10^{-10}$	-
8	20	m	кг	$32,5968 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2,26 \cdot 10^{-7}$	-
9	21	V_n^k	m^3	$7,3436 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$7,20 \cdot 10^{-10}$	-
10	22	t	$^{\circ}C$	185,69	$1,67 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-
11	22	t_0	$^{\circ}C$	20,00	$1,67 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-
12	22	ρ_n	$кг \cdot м^{-3}$	766,1	$8,61 \cdot 10^{-2}$	0,2 (0,025 %)

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TECHNOLOGICAL ASSURANCE OF SURFACE QUALITY IN MICRO/NANO SCALE

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Introduction. One of the most important requirements of today's modern and economical mass production methods is that the machine parts are produced within interchangeability. For this purpose, the tolerance is of great importance not only for the shape or size of the workpieces but also for the surface properties. The control of whether the workpieces have enough of these features should be accurately identified and evaluated before the parts are put into use. Prior to the industrial revolution, craftspeople served as fabricators and inspections and were entirely responsible for the quality of their products. Inspection was not a separate function in production [1]. In the philosophy of modern productions and of production metrology, inspections were separated from production and this headed to the existence of separate departments in facilities responsible for quality control.

All machining processes leave characteristic topographic features on the surfaces of components. Surface finishing is a very wide range of industrial processes. These processes change and modify the surface of produced sample to reach the desired properties. From deburring processes to a variety of technological processes, surface finishing covers a wide-ranging

of industries and applications. The main functions of the surface finishing are the improvement of the surface appearance, the enhancement of the corrosion resistance and the impartment of the required surface properties [2].

Surface finish occurs during the manufacturing process. For precise manufacturing, surface finish topological characterization methods are divided into two categories. These are contact and non-contact measurement and evaluation methods. These methods have pros and cons in different aspects. The technological developments are bringing new approaches and solutions. Therefore, evaluation methods for surface characterization should be revised and adapted to new approaching or emerging technologies. From coarse to very fine surface finishes, it is important to test a specimen with proper instruments and to make decision with above mentioned measurement and inspection methods. Therefore, surface finishing and quality measurements can be done using surface inspection instruments. In surface finish measurement studies or in industry, crucial task is that the selection of proper measurement methods according to surface finish [3].

The first stylus profilometer was developed for the surface topographical characterization by G. Schmaltz in 1929 [4]. After G. Schmaltz, Dr. E. Abbott in 1936 and Taylor Hobson in 1939 advanced the surface inspection & measurement know-how [5]. Early stage evaluation methods were insufficient in order to put a numerical value to the surface texture. Stylus profilometers advanced the evaluation methodologies and gave an opportunity to measure the surface parameters for finer and smoother surfaces quantitatively.

The invention of non-contact optical techniques is in a sense due to the drawbacks of the contact type stylus measurement techniques. These non-contact measurement methods have ability to measure in-process and the different types of materials. The optical systems and the stylus profilometers are two complementary methods [2]. From naked eye to the sophisticated scanning probe microscopes, the surface parameters for the evaluation of surface texture are developed according to the standards. Developments in manufacturing technology nowadays allow the production of technical parts that predict surface roughness under micrometers and nanometers. Microstructure of such surfaces can be measured at the sub-level of the nanometer by means of devices such as AFM and electron microscopes.

Roughness average (R_a) is the commonly used parameter for surface texture. The roughness average is the area between the roughness profile and its central line, or the integral of the absolute value of the roughness profile height over the sampling length. A cutoff long enough to include five complete sets of tool marks is desirable to obtain a good average roughness measurement. Determination of R_a is normally computed by the software but can be derived using the following formula:

$$Ra = \frac{1}{l_r} \int_0^{l_r} |z(x)| dx \quad (1)$$

where $z(x)$ is the profile deviation from the mean line and l_r is the sampling length [6].

Average Maximum Height of the Profile (R_z) is calculated by measuring the vertical distance from the highest peak to the lowest valley within five sampling lengths, then averaging these distances. R_z averages only the five highest peaks and the five deepest valleys - therefore extremes have a much greater influence on the final value [6].

Material and method. The aim of this study is to validate the surface roughness values of ten (10) standard reference samples having periodic and random surface profiles. Using a roughness tester and a 3D optical measuring system (Confocal Microscope), the evaluation of surfaces with different surface roughness classes produced by traditional machining methods (turning and milling) was performed. As a result, it was observed that two instruments produced the different roughness results depending upon the instruments' specifications (accuracy, precision etc.). Also, machining processes resulted in different surface texture.

The experimental studies of this study were performed at the Measurement Lab of Aydın Adnan Menderes University. In the experimental part of this study, inspection and assessment of roughness of various machined samples were done by using a roughness tester and an optical instrument. The contact instrument uses a stylus traversing the sample surface to evaluate the profile while the optical instrument utilizes a light beam for scanning the sample surface to acquire roughness data.

The contact roughness measurement of the metal surfaces was performed by surface roughness tester according to the ISO 4287 [7] by mapping the readings taken in a direction perpendicular to the direction of lay by calculating of the parameters R_a from a standard spectrum of roughness. Table 1 represents the specifications of the surface roughness tester.

The roughness measurement process of this experimental study is presented by utilizing the professional process management software toolbox 'iGrafx' [8]. The aim here is modeling a flowchart of the measurement process in order to obtain the roughness result for a certain measurement point of a given sample. The basic features for creating a process map in iGrafx are shown. There are more options by which the process map can be visually modified. Figure 1 depicts all of the activities that took place in the process of the roughness measurement.

The scenario in process map defines the simulation environment for the model. The simulation of this measurement process includes the resources being used and time duration for each activity for the evaluation of surface roughness measurement.

In this simulated example, there are two workers responsible for the laboratory work. The measurement activities that took place in the Measurement Lab of Aydın Adnan Menderes University were executed by myself and co-worker while this study was accomplished. In this simulation, it refers to three different people responsible being for the performing this process. Table 1 depicts the parameters for each activity involved in this measurement process at a single point for a given sample [9].

In order to run a simulation of the measurement process, the parameters for decision, resources, time and generator must be defined. In this case, the decision of "OK" was expressed in a statistical form in which the 75% of surface measurement results were rejected and measured again while the 25% of them proceeded to the next activity as an input [9].

Results and discussion. The measurement and assessment processes of this research work were carried out in Aydın Adnan Menderes University, Mechanical Engineering Department, Measurement Laboratory. The experiments were done by preparing flat specimens. Ten flat samples with different machining processes (turning and milling), having periodic and random profiles with different roughness value classes were used in this experimental study [9].

Figure 1. Process map for surface measurement performed at the Measurement Lab of Aydın Adnan Menderes University [9]

Table 1. Parameters defined in the simulation of a measurement process [9]

Nr.	Activity	Time Duration	Expression of “OK”	Resources (Workers)
1	Sample Choice	30-60 min	-	1
2	Measurement Preparation	5-10 min	-	2
3	Surface Measurement 2D Roughness Parameters	1-3 min	-	2
4	Decision of “OK”	5-10 min	75% “No” 25% “Yes”	1
5	Surface Roughness Characterization	10-17 min	-	2
6	Measurement Preparation NanoFocus μsurf explorer	15-20 min	-	2
7	Surface Measurement 2D & 3D Roughness Parameters	2-4 min	-	2
8	Decision of “OK”	7-15 min	Decision of “OK”	1
9	Surface Roughness Characterization	20-28 min	-	2
10	Comparison	15-20 min	-	1
11	Evaluation & Interpretation	10-20 min	-	1

Milled and turned steel samples having periodic and random surface profiles were illustrated in Figure 2 and the technical drawing of one of the reference samples was represented in Figure 3.

The results of these samples taken from the surface roughness tester (Figure 4) are presented in the following tables (Tables 2-5) [9]. Tables 2 and 3 indicate the roughness measurement results obtained from the measurements using roughness tester and catalogue as R_a and R_z . Tables 4 and 5 show the roughness measurement findings obtained from the measurements using 3d optical system (NanoFocus μsurf Explorer) and catalogue as R_a and R_z .

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. Milling (a) and Turning (b) steel samples [9]

Figure 3. Technical drawing of one of the reference samples [9]

Figure 4. Surface roughness tester [9,10]

Tables 2 and 3 present the roughness measurement results of turned and milled samples using roughness tester. As it can be found from Tables 2 and 3, variations belonging to the milled samples are smaller than those of the turned samples.

Table 2. Roughness measurement results by Roughness Tester (Turned Samples) [9]

R_a/R_z	1.3	6.5	2.2	9.8	5.4	20	10	41	20	78
	$R_a=1.3 \setminus R_z=6.5$		$R_a=2.2 \setminus R_z=9.8$		$R_a=5.4 \setminus R_z=20$		$R_a=10 \setminus R_z=41$		$R_a=20 \setminus R_z=78$	
	R_a	R_z	R_a	R_z	R_a	R_z	R_a	R_z	R_a	R_z
1	1.387	4.141	2.630	11.500	4.450	16.100	8.700	40.700	17.200	70.200
2	1.763	4.971	2.560	11.500	4.520	16.400	9.230	40.700	16.100	70.900
3	0.907	5.184	2.580	11.400	4.730	17.100	8.700	39.500	15.830	70.700
4	0.702	6.102	2.520	11.200	4.780	17.000	7.360	41.200	15.300	67.900
5	1.024	6.751	2.440	11.800	4.770	17.800	8.490	38.700	18.300	70.200
Std Dev	0.421	1.016	0.071	0.217	0.154	0.661	0.691	1.029	1.201	1.203

Table 3. Roughness measurement results by Roughness Tester (Milled Samples) [9]

R_a/R_z	0.89	6.5	2.1	11	4.8	20	9.8	41	18	78
	$R_a=0.89 \setminus R_z=6.5$		$R_a=2.1 \setminus R_z=11$		$R_a=4.8 \setminus R_z=20$		$R_a=9.8 \setminus R_z=41$		$R_a=18 \setminus R_z=78$	
	R_a	R_z	R_a	R_z	R_a	R_z	R_a	R_z	R_a	R_z
1	0.898	5.230	2.190	10.300	4.900	19.000	8.010	38.700	10.700	74.000
2	0.843	5.040	2.130	10.700	5.000	18.800	8.450	38.900	10.600	74.300
3	0.891	5.080	2.160	9.080	5.310	19.500	8.130	39.300	10.700	73.900
4	0.811	4.990	2.170	10.100	5.010	19.100	8.620	40.500	10.900	75.500
5	0.872	4.800	2.060	9.930	4.940	19.000	8.030	38.800	10.600	74.200
Std Dev	0.036	0.156	0.051	0.600	0.162	0.259	0.273	0.740	0.122	0.646

Tables 4 and 5 give the roughness measurement results of turned and milled samples using NanoFocus μ surf Explorer. As it can be concluded from Tables 4 and 5, the standard deviations belonging to the milled samples have less variable than those of the turned samples.

Table 4. Roughness measurement results by NanoFocus μ surf Explorer (Turned Samples) [9]

R_a/R_z	1.3	6.5	2.2	9.8	5.4	20	10	41	20	78
	$R_a=1.3 \setminus R_z=6.5$		$R_a=2.2 \setminus R_z=9.8$		$R_a=5.4 \setminus R_z=20$		$R_a=10 \setminus R_z=41$		$R_a=20 \setminus R_z=78$	
	R_a	R_z	R_a	R_z	R_a	R_z	R_a	R_z	R_a	R_z
1	1.297	6.410	2.213	9.910	5.445	20.110	10.171	40.970	19.620	78.120
2	1.363	6.710	2.256	9.880	5.510	20.240	10.030	40.550	19.810	77.950
3	1.257	6.840	2.258	9.880	5.412	20.210	9.997	41.150	20.130	78.750
4	1.322	6.520	2.252	10.120	5.378	20,01	10.096	41.200	20.300	78.870
5	1.324	6.510	2.244	10.180	5.477	20.180	10.290	40.870	19.940	78.110
Std Dev	0.039	0.173	0.018	0.144	0.052	0.056	0.118	0.259	0.266	0.418

Table 5. Roughness measurement results by NanoFocus μ surf Explorer (Milled Samples) [9]

R_a/R_z	0.89	6.5	2.1	11	4.8	20	9.8	41	18	78
	$R_a=0.89 \setminus R_z=6.5$		$R_a=2.1 \setminus R_z=11$		$R_a=4.8 \setminus R_z=20$		$R_a=9.8 \setminus R_z=41$		$R_a=18 \setminus R_z=78$	
	R_a	R_z	R_a	R_z	R_a	R_z	R_a	R_z	R_a	R_z
1	0.899	6.430	2.190	10.990	4.990	19.900	9.710	40.700	17.870	77.960
2	0.893	6.440	2.180	10.798	4.890	18.800	9.850	40.900	17.760	77.790
3	0.891	6.480	2.185	11.080	4.981	19.890	9.830	40.400	17.790	77.990
4	0.891	6.490	2.210	11.001	5.010	19.100	9.720	40.500	17.900	78.090
5	0.892	6.500	2.215	10.980	4.899	20.000	9.630	40.800	17.860	78.110
Std Dev	0.003	0.031	0.016	0.104	0.055	0.088	0.091	0.207	0.059	0.128

Figure 5. NanoFocus μ surf explorer [9,11]

Figure 6. 2D Topography, Roughness Parameters from NanoFocus μ surf explorer and 3D Topography [9]

Five consecutive measurements were performed for milled and turned steel samples, respectively. The results of these samples taken from NanoFocus μ surf explorer (Figure 5) are given (Tables 4 and 5). Figure 6 indicates 2D topography, roughness parameters and a 3D topography [9].

These experimental study indicates that there has been a trivial difference between the surface roughness tester (contact) and the optical (non-contact) measurement systems on engineering surfaces but considerable differences between them on some very fine surfaces statistically. The results from many tests showed that there has been a correlation between the surface roughness and the properties of the surface topography [9].

Conclusions. The instruments used in this experimental practice are a roughness tester and a confocal microscope. Ten different samples make it possible to examine the different types of measurement instruments in terms of surfaces with different forms and machining techniques. As a result, it could be said that the surface roughness measurements obtained by using two different types of measuring instruments on these reference surfaces with different machining techniques show quite good matching. It was observed that two instruments produced the different roughness results depending upon the instruments' specifications (accuracy, precision etc.). Additionally, machining processes resulted in different surface texture. In the production of standard samples, precise manufacturing should be necessary by controlling manufacturing parameters. In conclusion, these two instruments employ different operating principles. A tester acts like a ball touching a surface while an optical instrument benefits from the reflection of an electromagnetic wave of LED light beams delivered to the surface. Nevertheless, it is possible to get more precise measurement results from using an optical instrument as opposed to a roughness tester [9].

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ПОВЕРКА И КАЛИБРОВКА КООРДИНАТНО ИЗМЕРИТЕЛЬНЫХ МАШИН С ПОМОЩЬЮ ВЫСОКОТОЧНОЙ ИНТЕРФЕРЕНЦИОННОЙ ИЗМЕРИТЕЛЬНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ

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В настоящее время в области измерений геометрических параметров широко распространены координатно-измерительные машины (КИМ) различных габаритных размеров и точностных характеристик.

Все машины должны проходить процедуру поверки/калибровки для подтверждения своих метрологических характеристик.

На данный момент поверка в нашей стране осуществляется по действующим документам, гармонизированным с ISO 10360-2, согласно которым, основным средством поверки КИМ используется материальная мера типа концевая мера длины (КМД) длиной не менее 2/3 от измерительного объема.

Как известно КМД производятся до 1 м, поэтому при поверке крупногабаритных КИМ более метра возникают трудности при передаче единицы длины.

Данную проблему можно решить двумя способами – либо использовать меры типа ball-bar, либо использовать интерференционные установки.

При использовании мер типа ball-bar более 1 м, существуют определенные трудности, связанные с:
- аттестацией длин, особенно когда мера составная;